

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

NURSE BURNOUT AND WORK CONDITIONS

Zahraa Abdulkarim AL Nass¹, Rawan Ghazi Al Hammad², Fedaa Ahmed Al-Zaher¹, Aida Ali Abdulwahab¹, Fahima Luqman Aldawoud¹, Ahmed Salah AlNujaim³, Amal Habib Al suliman¹, Dalal Abdullah Al Fandi³, Manal Taher AlAli¹, Fatimah Ali Alzahir³, Houriah Abdullah hussien Tarmoukh¹, Dalal Ahmed Ali Albandri¹, Zahra Abdulkaram AlNas¹,
Nada Abdulmohsen Al Faraj¹, Mohammed Marai Ali Al-dukain¹

¹ Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital - National Guard Hospital – Dammam – Saudi Arabia

² National Guard Hospital - Al Ahsa – Saudi Arabia

³ Primary healthcare - National Guard Hospital – Dammam – Saudi Arabia

Article Received: November 2021 **Accepted:** November 2021 **Published:** December 2021

Abstract:

Nurse burnout, characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment, significantly impacts nurses' well-being, job satisfaction, and care quality. Various factors, including high strain, demanding work conditions, dispositional optimism, and life satisfaction, contribute to burnout, emphasizing the importance of tailored support and intervention. Organizational factors like poor work environments are also linked to higher burnout rates, highlighting the need to enhance work conditions to alleviate burnout and improve care quality.

Keywords: Burnout – Nurses – Covid-19

Corresponding author:

Zahraa Abdulkarim AL Nass,

Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital - National Guard Hospital

– Dammam – Saudi Arabia

QR code

Please cite this article in press Zahraa Abdulkarim AL Nass et al, *Nurse Burnout And Work Conditions*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2021; 08(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Nurse burnout is a multifaceted issue characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. It significantly impacts nurses' quality of life, job satisfaction, and care quality. Studies indicate that burnout is prevalent among nurses globally, with approximately 42% of nurses in Portugal, Spain, and Brazil experiencing moderate to high levels of burnout, with Spain showing the highest levels of depersonalization. [1] Diverse factors contribute to burnout, including high mental and physical strain, demanding work conditions, and personal attributes such as dispositional optimism and life satisfaction. Notably, emotional exhaustion is more pronounced among nurses with medium life satisfaction and those with a pessimistic outlook, highlighting the need for individualized support and intervention. [2] Organizational factors also play a

crucial role; a study in Chile found a significant association between poor work environments and higher burnout rates, suggesting that improving the work environment could mitigate burnout and enhance care quality. [3] Moreover, burnout is not only a personal issue but also an organizational one, as it affects overall nursing performance and the economic aspects of healthcare systems. In West Java, a study revealed that depersonalization was the most significant contributor to burnout among inpatient nurses. At the same time, emotional exhaustion was relatively low, and personal accomplishment was high, indicating a complex interplay of factors influencing burnout. [4] The relationship between burnout and quality of life is well-documented. Most studies find that higher burnout levels are associated with poorer quality of life among nurses, necessitating interventional programs to improve both aspects.

Figure (1): Aspects of Burnout

Burnout and Quality of Life:

As mentioned previously, burnout in the nursing department is a multifaceted syndrome characterized

by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a reduced sense of personal accomplishment, significantly impacting nurses' quality of life (QoL).

Emotional exhaustion refers to feeling emotionally overextended and depleted of emotional resources. At the same time, depersonalization involves an impersonal response towards the recipients of one's care. A reduced sense of personal accomplishment denotes a decline in feelings of competence and achievement in one's work with people. [5,6] Quality of life, on the other hand, encompasses the overall well-being of nurses, including physical, mental, and social health dimensions. It is influenced by job burnout, perceived social support, psychological hardiness, and work-life quality (QWL). [7,8] Studies have shown a significant negative correlation between burnout and QoL, indicating that higher levels of burnout are associated with lower QoL among nurses. [5,9,10] Factors such as high workloads, monotonous work designs, and inadequate staffing contribute to burnout, which in turn deteriorates the QoL of nurses. Additionally, socio-demographic variables like age, marital status, and work shifts also play a role in influencing both burnout and QoL. For instance, nurses working in primary care, urban areas, and those

on rotating shifts are more prone to compassion fatigue and burnout, which negatively affects their QoL. [11,12] Conversely, factors like perceived social support and psychological empowerment can mitigate the effects of burnout and enhance QoL by fostering a supportive work environment and promoting a sense of control and competence among nurses. [7,8] The relationship between burnout and QoL is also mediated by the quality of the work environment, with a conducive and harmonious work atmosphere crucial in minimizing burnout and improving QoL. Interventions to reduce burnout and enhance QoL should focus on optimizing nurse staffing, providing reasonable compensation, establishing appropriate shift schedules, and fostering a supportive work culture. [10,11] Overall, addressing burnout and improving QoL in the nursing department requires a comprehensive approach that considers individual and organizational factors to ensure the well-being of nurses and the quality of patient care they provide.

Figure (2): Burnout Reflect

Burnout and Job Satisfaction:

Nurses' burnout and job satisfaction are intricately linked, with numerous studies highlighting the multifaceted nature of this relationship. Workload and burnout directly affect job satisfaction and turnover intentions, with burnout being a more significant predictor of turnover than workload alone. [13] For instance, a study involving 594 nurses found a positive correlation between burnout and the rationing of nursing care, and a negative correlation between job satisfaction and the rationing of care, indicating that burnout can lead to decreased job satisfaction and adverse patient outcomes. [14] These findings suggest that addressing burnout through supportive measures, professional development, and a positive organizational culture can significantly improve job

satisfaction among nurses, ultimately benefiting both the healthcare providers and the patients they serve.

Burnout and Quality of Care:

Nurse burnout is a multifaceted issue that significantly impacts the quality of patient care. Studies have shown that higher levels of burnout among nurses correlate with lower job satisfaction and poorer patient care quality. The consequences of burnout are severe, leading to suboptimal patient care, increased medical errors, and adverse patient outcomes. For instance, a study on critical care nurses found a significant negative correlation between burnout and quality of life, indicating that higher burnout levels are associated with poorer quality of care. [5] The practice environment and work characteristics also play a crucial role; positive environments and favorable work

conditions can lower burnout and improve patient outcomes, while leader support is essential in shaping a positive perception of the practice environment and reducing burnout. [15]

Burnout During Covid-19:

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly exacerbated burnout among nurses. Studies have shown that nurses on the frontline, particularly those in intensive care units, experienced high levels of burnout due to increased workload, prolonged use of personal protective equipment (PPE), and the emotional toll of treating severely ill patients. [16-18] A systematic review highlighted that female nurses and younger nurses were particularly vulnerable to burnout and PTSD, with factors such as work-related stress, physical strain from PPE, and mental health concerns being significant contributors. Comparative studies revealed that while burnout levels did not significantly change from pre-pandemic times, anxiety, stress, and depression among nurses increased markedly during the first wave of the pandemic, indicating a complex interplay between burnout and other mental health issues. [19] The prevalence of burnout was notably high, with studies reporting that 40% of nurses experienced high levels of burnout, and factors such as PPE and increased workload were

significant predictors. [18] Resilience emerged as a crucial protective factor, with higher resilience associated with lower burnout levels and better coping mechanisms during the pandemic. However, resilience levels varied, with male nurses and those with higher educational qualifications exhibiting greater resilience. [20] The integrated model of compassion satisfaction-compassion fatigue and empowerment also provided insights into how work-related variables like co-worker support, job satisfaction, and exposure to violence influenced burnout and quality of life among pediatric nurses. Additionally, the economic collapse in regions like Lebanon further compounded the stress and burnout experienced by nurses, highlighting the need for systemic support and resilience-building programs. [20] The emotional fatigue dimension of burnout was inversely correlated with resilience, suggesting that enhancing resilience could mitigate burnout's adverse effects. Factors such as age, gender, education, and length of work were also identified as correlates of burnout, with younger and less experienced nurses being more susceptible. [21] Overall, the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the critical need for systemic changes to protect nurses from burnout and ensure their well-being during such unprecedented times.

Figure (3): Factors Contribute to Burnout

REFERENCES:

1. Borges EMdN, Queirós CML, Abreu MdSNd, et al.: Burnout among nurses: a multicentric comparative study. *Revista latino-americana de enfermagem*. 2021, 29:e3432.
2. Zborowska A, Gurowiec PJ, Młynarska A, Uchmanowicz I: Factors affecting occupational burnout among nurses including job satisfaction, life satisfaction, and life orientation: a cross-sectional study. *Psychology research and behavior management*. 2021:1761-1777.
3. Simonetti M, Aqueveque AMV, Alejandra Galiano M: Environment, workload, and nurse burnout in public hospitals in Chile. *Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da USP*. 2021, 55:e20200521.

4. Manullang ND, Sitanggang YF, Panjaitan MA: BURNOUT SYNDROME OF NURSES IN INPATIENT UNITS. *Nursing Current: Jurnal Keperawatan*. 2021, 9:9-16.
5. Alotni MA, Elgazzar SE: Investigation of burnout, its associated factors and its effect on the quality of life of critical care nurses working in Buraydah Central Hospital at Qassim Region, Saudi Arabia. *The Open Nursing Journal*. 2020, 14.
6. Naz S, Hashmi AM, Asif A: Burnout and quality of life in nurses of a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan. *J Pak Med Assoc*. 2016, 66:532-536.
7. Hatamipour K, Hoveida F, Rahimaghaee F, Babaeiamiri N, Ashoori J: The Nurses' Quality of Life Based on Burnout, Perceived Social Support and Psychological Hardiness. *Journal of Research Development in Nursing and Midwifery*. 2017, 14:22-28. [10.29252/jgbrnm.14.1.22](https://doi.org/10.29252/jgbrnm.14.1.22)
8. Permarupan PY, Al Mamun A, Samy NK, Saufi RA, Hayat N: Predicting Nurses Burnout through Quality of Work Life and Psychological Empowerment: A Study Towards Sustainable Healthcare Services in Malaysia. *Sustainability*. 2020, 12:388.
9. Elias Abdel-Aziz A, Saied Adam S: Relationship between Resilience, Burnout and Professional Quality of Life among Nurses Working at El-Abbassiya Psychiatric-Mental Health Hospital. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*. 2020, 11:551-577. [10.21608/ejhc.2020.156951](https://doi.org/10.21608/ejhc.2020.156951)
10. HALVANI GH, IZADPANAH A, MIHANPOUR H, ESMAEELI A: The relationship between job burnout and quality of life of nurses in Khatam-al-Anbia, Gonbad-e-Kavoos hospital in 2017. *Occupational Hygiene and Health Promotion Journal*. 2018, 2:1-13.
11. Wang Q-Q, Lv W-J, Qian R-L, Zhang Y-H: Job burnout and quality of working life among Chinese nurses: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Nursing Management*. 2019, 27:1835-1844. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.12884>
12. Ruiz-Fernández MD, Pérez-García E, Ortega-Galán ÁM: Quality of Life in Nursing Professionals: Burnout, Fatigue, and Compassion Satisfaction. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2020, 17:1253.
13. Dwinijanti L, Adhikara MFA, Kusumapradja R: Job satisfaction and turnover intention among public sector nurses: Is workload and burnout the issue? *JEMA: Jurnal Ilmiah Bidang Akuntansi dan Manajemen*. 2020, 17:67-77. [10.31106/jema.v17i1.4951](https://doi.org/10.31106/jema.v17i1.4951)
14. Uchmanowicz I, Karniej P, Lisiak M, et al.: The relationship between burnout, job satisfaction and the rationing of nursing care—A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Nursing Management*. 2020, 28:2185-2195. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.13135>
15. Gensimore MM, Maduro RS, Morgan MK, McGee GW, Zimbro KS: The Effect of Nurse Practice Environment on Retention and Quality of Care via Burnout, Work Characteristics, and Resilience: A Moderated Mediation Model. *JONA: The Journal of Nursing Administration*. 2020, 50.
16. Caruso R, Annaloro C, Arrigoni C, et al.: Burnout and post-traumatic stress disorder in frontline nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic: a systematic literature review and meta-analysis of studies published in 2020: COVID-19, burnout, and PTSD in nurses. *Acta Biomedica Atenei Parmensis*. 2021, 92:e2021428. [10.23750/abm.v92iS2.11796](https://doi.org/10.23750/abm.v92iS2.11796)
17. Seluch M, Volchansky M, Safronov R: RETRACTED: Dependence of emotional burnout on personality typology in the COVID-19 pandemic. *Work*. 2021, 70:713-721. [10.3233/WOR-210428](https://doi.org/10.3233/WOR-210428)
18. Kabunga A, Okalo P: Prevalence and predictors of burnout among nurses during COVID-19: a cross-sectional study in hospitals in central Uganda. *BMJ Open*. 2021, 11:e054284. [10.1136/bmjopen-2021-054284](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-054284)
19. Zakeri MA, Rahiminezhad E, Salehi F, Ganjeh H, Dehghan M: Burnout, anxiety, stress, and depression among Iranian nurses: Before and during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 2021, 12:789737.
20. Alameddine M, Clinton M, Bou-Karroum K, Richa N, Doumit MAA: Factors Associated With the Resilience of Nurses During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*. 2021, 18:320-331. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12544>
21. Melike, Yönder, Ertem., Sevinc, Capa., Mehmet, Karakaş., Hülya, Ensari., Ayşegül, Koç.: Investigation of the Relationship Between Nurses' Burnout and Psychological Resilience Levels. *Clinical and Experimental Health Sciences*. 2020, 10(1):9-15. doi: [10.33808/CLINEXPHEALTHSCI.600924](https://doi.org/10.33808/CLINEXPHEALTHSCI.600924)